

ANALYSIS OF IMAGES NATURE IN WRITERS'S PROSAIC WORK

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Abstract. *Shukur Kholmirzaev is considered one of the creators of a unique style in Uzbek literature of the twentieth century. With his work Shukur Kholmirzaev entered to Uzbek literature in the 60s. He won the hearts of students with his first stories. The stories he created attracted the attention of Abdullah Kahhor. In the given article the nature of images in the prose works of Shukur Kholmirzaev using the examples of the stories “The Old Man” and “Smile” are analyzed.*

Keywords: *image, character, artistic texture, writing skills, fact of life, life event, writer's fantasy, death, struggle, conscience, betrayal of trust, work, money, honesty, retelling, smile.*

It is important to suggest that representing reality in a figurative image is one of the main features of literature and art. Figurative reflection requires showing the general, natural aspects of life in individuals, events, and certain emotions [10, 33].

The image is the result of the embodiment of real life in fiction. They only reflect not only real life, but also express a general idea. In it, the author not only shows how he saw real life, but also creates his own strange new world, like an artist. “The dynamic combination of heterogeneous features of an image is determined by its dominant, or, in other words, its core, which is formed during the period of creative work, where the main idea of both the entire work and its individual parts emerges. The main idea of a work, ideas about its individual parts, foundations and images may change, take a different form, but its fundamental principle remains the same, and it combines all the artistic features of the work. After the creative idea has fully matured, the emotional capabilities of the writer increase during the period when he begins to work” [11,80]. An artistic image is a phenomenon processed by the author’s imagination. The image can be understood as a separate part of the whole idea. Based on this, the following situation serves as the criterion for the image.

- a) an artistic image is a reflection of existence in our thinking;
- b) the image is inseparable from the prototype and reflects the creative thought of the author;
- c) an artistic image helps to understand some features of the author’s worldview. With its help, the reader understands the author's point of view when analyzing the text;
- d) the image also has a symbolic meaning. They can be interpreted in different ways. In this case, the student’s opinion is important.

According to observations, aspiring artists are turning more to the narrative genre. It does not look for causes of causes, like other epic genres. The plot does not become multi-faceted, multi-linear. But sometimes this happens in stories. But in most cases, a multi-faceted, multi-layered story can turn a story into a novel. The plot is mostly linear. Words are connected with thoughts by an internal connection. The status of the word sense varies depending on the level of talent. The main dimensions of literature are taken in relation to the work of these artists. They approach the divine word with divine inspiration.

Shukur Kholmirzaev's stories "The Old Man" and "Smile" invite observation with their closeness to real life. The heroes of the work are not fictional characters, old man Koziboy, father Jalil, butcher Cain, but believers, the plot is also based on a real event.

Koziboy in the writer's story "The Old Man" depicts a man, who works honestly all his life and brings benefit to people, and through the image of a butcher, Cain depicts the character of a man, who betrays his trust. The nature of these two images is opposite to each other. One likes to benefit people through honest work, while the other considers betrayal to be a normal situation. The world itself consists of these two opposing forces. One enjoys pain and the other enjoys pleasure. The result, as a product of the writer's skill, created a very impressive picture of mental suffering. Indeed, the fact that against all actions of the heart there is its opposite - the evil of the heart - fills the reader with deep thought.

Shukur Kholmirzaev does not use any romance in the story "The Old Man". The writer tried to show national traditions and national values in his works at a high level.

Expressing the national spirit in his works, the writer shows the traditions and customs of the Uzbek people using the example of the Surkhan oasis. In his works he tried to express the way of life of a certain region, customs, dialect, landscape, that is, through the image of nature. It turned out that Shukur Kholmirzaev Surkhan is a very talented person who knows the life, living conditions, customs, culture and history of the inhabitants of the oasis and can write about them with confidence. He is a well-known and recognized artist, who combined in his works various aspects of the life of the people and interpreted them in the national spirit, creating a series of works based on the national mentality and identity of the people.

"Old Koziboy is thin, his legs are like stilettos. While walking, he turns his head in all directions and makes sudden movements, as if screaming. He looks at people seriously. Entering the teahouse, he asks about his descendants and ancestors. By the way, the old man is lucky even when the worker comes out: after all, the mountain comrades, carrying sacks with the worker on their donkeys, are also clients of the old man Koziboy! They are not heavy and "hardy", like the population of the center of the region. Instead of buying their goods in bulk, they sell them in bulk and rush back, buying what they need: the mountain is far away, they need to reach their village ahead of time. Then elderly Koziboy will become their best friend. However, it makes little use of this flexibility. Carried away by trade, he does not even suspect that he was selling "five for ten shillings." However, this does not stop the work. Especially at night, when he starts drying and selling the chord near the cinema, he is very happy, like the others" [8, 152].

The hero of the play, the elderly Koziboy, four years after the death of his old woman, is overcome by the fear of death. He began to live in fear of death. Everywhere he looks, everything seems to be the specter of death. It's so superficial. In fact, the old man is afraid not of death, but of uncontrollable death, and the money that he has saved for years, he gives to the butcher Cain to die, who believes that it belongs to him. "Every now and then he walks into the butcher shop and asks, 'How are you doing?' he pretends that the money is safe. The butcher also scratched his short chin and said, "Calm down!" speaks [8, 152-153].

At first glance, the character of old man Gooseboy in the story seems to be a very simple, carefree character. But as we mentioned above, as we read the story, thoughts about the work change radically. In the eyes of the reader, there are usually two old men under seventy years of age sitting in the grid of their home, not practicing any profession. But we see the complete opposite of these characteristics in the hero of the play, old man Koziboy.

Believing him to be dead, he gives his friend Cain to the butcher. Cain the Butcher abuses trust, leaving the reader feeling there is nothing to worry about because a solution has been found. Old Goatboy, don't leave my corpse on the street, tell the waiter to let him know how I feel. They say that you will spend the money that I gave you for my death on maracas, but you can't see with your eyes that there is no trace of either the money or the butcher's conscience. The butcher has already spent it on his own needs. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the butcher's act became "Motivation" for old man Koziboy, in modern terms.

"I will have to work again. I need to earn honest money. I have to die, if I die after this, it's a different matter," he pulled himself together. He got up in the middle of the night and fried the meat. Sugar woke up in the morning, went down to the stream and washed himself. He freshened up and went out into the street, elderly Koziboy became the same as before" [8, 156].

Father Jalil, the hero of the story "Smile", was once deceived by the tempting promises and slogans of Shura. In his old age he was bedridden due to cancer. The elderly man learns about this through his granddaughter Sadaf, the only daughter of his only son. This is how he remembers his past days one by one.

In exchange for the services rendered by brother Jalil, the badge was made, "he will not receive a piece of the label." But he's not even upset about it.

There are three-character systems in this story. Jalil and Kuyun are people of the same character, and Momin and Jalil's father's son Shakir are a different character system. The story focuses on the struggle of these characters. The work depicts the clash of love for the Motherland and selfishness. The country asked Kuyun to be selfless, and he sacrificed his life without hesitation. Momin decided to betray, he also achieved his goal and received all the privileges of the new government.

This story is just one example of falsification of history. Times have changed. Patriotic Kuyun was destroyed as an enemy of the people and his name was forgotten. The hypocrite Momin became a national hero. No one except Jalil knows who Mumin really was. And Jalil does not sell it, as he promised Kuyunu.

The rabbit is not an isolated phenomenon. He is the common image of all nationalist fighters in the history of our country. The writer portrays him as a man with a big heart, pure faith and a strong person. Reading the story, the reader knows that Jalil, who came in the form of a dervish, is a red man, and Momin, who was a qalandar before him, is also a traitor. He knows and for some reason observes their behavior. He acts as if he has no choice but to think and observe.

Compared to the rabbit, these two young people look very small, weak and helpless. They are like bait caught in a trap. But still, Kün surrenders of his own free will and, looking for the last time at the mountains, peaks, and the ground strewn with bones, he stands up and orders the young men to tie his hands : "When I used to think that the Motherland was lost, I would have gone down earlier myself. Which is enough for the martyr to leave" [9,112].

In the work, Kuyun is embodied as a symbol of courage. He acts like a true believer, that is, he bravely faces death.

Shukur Kholmiraev effectively uses various artistic and visual means in his works.

We want to think about one such tool that seems new to us. We tentatively called this art-visual tool "bad results of good intentions." The same artistic and visual instrument is present in the story "Smile," which we just looked at.

There are several scenes and views in the work that will excite the reader. There is such a scene: a rabbit breeder is brought to the market, that is, to the court, at his request, for trial. The writer describes this painful and sad scene as follows: “While the crowd stood around, the Revolutionary Committee of the Cheka and the village council asked the leader Orzikhodzha Kuyun two questions.

- Why did you fight?

- “For religion...” said the printer Rabbit.

Orzihoja looked at the teachers, Sufis and imams of the mosque standing in a row next to the representatives.

- What is the punishment for a bully rabbit?

- Scientist! Scientist! - They said.

Orzihoja asked Kuyun again:

- Why did you fight again?

Rabbit head:

-“For the people,” he said.

- People! - Orzikhodzha exclaimed. - What is the punishment for a bully rabbit?

“Death, death!” [9, 113]

In this episode, there is a big difference in the attitude of Rabbit and those around him towards life. We are witnesses that the efforts of Kuyun Gorbashi for the benefit of religion and the people caused harm to both religious people and the people themselves.

Rabbit hunter is an extremely bright link in the series of created characters by Shukur Kholmiraev. The title of the story “Smile” may confuse the reader at first glance. The reader who starts reading the story does not fully understand the secret of the smile. Because there is no event that will make you smile. What can Father Jalil, the hero of the play, who was deceived all his life and lived in poverty, be proud of? There is no good reason to make him happy or smile.

The characters in the story are Momin - a traitor, Jalil - a lost but conscientious man, Orzikhodzha - a loyal soldier of the new government, sold to the Soviets. But his master also imprisoned him because he was one of the masters. Shakir is a selfish person who wants to live depending on someone else. But he can't understand it. He wants to replace his father's pride and anger with desire: the qualities of the father were not passed on to his son [7, 294-295].

The work skillfully shows not only different destinies, different characters, even discussions and disagreements between generations. A story about honor, shame and pride. The writer's stories are multi-valued, multi-layered, that is, polyphonic works. The first meaning that emerges from this story is the end of tyranny, the physical destruction of those who fought for the country, such as Quyun Korboshi, and the establishment of Soviet power. The second meaning is that the work depicts the struggle between truth and injustice. A believing old man becomes a hero because of his betrayal. The third meaning is that many sales will come from Jalil's head. He is not rewarded according to his deserts, on the contrary, he is “under the elbows” in many places. But still he remained true to his firm promise. He did not deviate from his ideas and life principles.

At the end of the story, Father Jalil leaves the world: “Everyone was horrified by the frozen smile on his face” [9,115]. This old man's smile is the result of life, life's journey. At the heart of this smile, it seems, his sins and merits, will and perseverance are embodied in a word, his faith. So Father Jalil laughs at this unfaithful world.

In general, the images created by Shukur Kholmirzaev in both works are clear and unique and at the same time contain common, typical features embodies, which in its turn increases the impact on the reader.

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